

IMPLEMENTATION OF INTEGRITY ZONE DEVELOPMENT AT THE INVESTMENT AND ONE-STOP INTEGRATED SERVICE OF BEKASI REGENCY

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to describe and analyze the implementation of the development of the integrity zone in the Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service Office of Bekasi Regency and to describe the influence of actors in the Integrity Zone development program. The type of research used is qualitative descriptive research. With the focus of the research referring to the Integrity Zone indicators and actors in the program. The data source was taken using a purposive sampling technique that determines the criteria according to the work team field. Data collection techniques range from observation, interviews, to documentation. The analysis techniques used are data reduction, data presentation, and drawing conclusions or verification. The conclusion of the results of this study is that the Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service Office of Bekasi Regency has a perception value of service quality that is Free from Corruption by its users. This can be seen from the Anti-Corruption Perception Index Value obtained of 3.82 and the Service Quality Perception Index Value obtained of 3.80. In addition, the Capital Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service Office of Bekasi Regency has implemented and committed to the integrity zone program by implementing 6 indicators, namely change management, governance, human resource management system, strengthening accountability, strengthening supervision, improving the quality of public services. The implementation of the Integrity Zone development has become a commitment in Bekasi Regency, to provide honest, accountable services that can improve the quality of human resources as part of the regulation. In addition, the assessment is also observed from the attitude of the implementer. In the implementation of the assessment, the role of the actor is considered quite good, because it is able to implement the rules regarding excellent service in accordance

with the existing Standard Operating Procedure.

Keywords: Implementation, Development and Integrity Zone.

INTRODUCTION

Corruption behavior has become worrying and threatens the sustainability of human life. Case after case of corruption has become a brand of news and public discussion that is never-ending, both locally and as an issue at the world level. Corruption has also become a phenomenon that has attracted the attention of the United Nations (UN), which concluded that corruption is determined as a crime that can damage the order of life. The impact of corruption crimes, apart from the economic aspect, corrupt behavior can threaten the noble values of human life in general (Sugiarto, 2022).

The United Nations implemented the Anti-Corruption Convention or United Nation Convention Against Corruption (UNCAC) in 2003. The convention is intended to prevent corruption from spreading massively throughout the world. Due to this threat, the UN made an agreement to find alternatives to combat and stop corrupt behavior globally. This threat is recognized because corruption has become a problem that is not only in one country, but has spread beyond the borders of the country, as stated in the preamble to the UNCAC, that corruption is believed to be no longer a local problem, but has become a phenomenon that affects all societies and has an impact on the economy, international cooperation. So that the UN council needs to prevent and control it as a step that is considered strategic (UNCAC, 2003). Upon the agreement of the UN UNCAC Convention above, in which Indonesia is a signatory, it must certainly be a leading country in eradicating and overcoming the phenomenon of corruption. Indonesia's commitment was then followed up by making regulations in 2003 by issuing Law (UU) No. 7 of 2006 concerning the UN Convention Against Corruption, 2003.

Indonesia's efforts to be free from corruption continue to be carried out, the Corruption Perception Index (CPI) continues to increase, most recently according to Transparency International, Indonesia's CPI in 2021 was 38 points (on a scale of 0-100). This condition increased by one point from 2020 by 37 points. In the global CPI position, Indonesia is ranked 96 out of 180 countries which is then considered better. So that this condition has improved compared to 2019 which was ranked 120. It is known that the survey measurement to see the CPI ranking score is by determining countries that are considered very corrupt with a value of 0, then countries that are categorized as free from corruption with a score of 100 (Pahlevi,

2022).

The increase in Indonesia's Corruption Perception Index does not yet show that Indonesia is free from the clutches of corrupt behavior. For example, assessments from anti-corruption activists such as ICW (Indonesia Corruption Watch) are of the view that the increase in Indonesia's CPI in 2021 is still considered false, which is mostly contributed by the economic sector, where the indicator for improving government governance is a false improvement (ICW, 2022). The commitment to being free from corruption continues to be carried out by the Indonesian Government. One of these efforts is by carrying out bureaucratic reform with the Integrity Zone (ZI) development program in Government Agencies. The program is an effort to carry out bureaucratic reform, as regulated in Presidential Regulation No. 81 of 2010 concerning the Grand Design of Bureaucratic Reform 2010-2025.

Bureaucratic reform can be a step in organizing a good, effective and efficient government system and reorganizing the bureaucratic process from the highest to the lowest level. Bureaucratic reform aims to correct several recurring errors between government functions, which involve human resources and their budgets. Furthermore, reorganizing the bureaucracy at various levels, and carrying out innovations gradually, realistically, concretely, and the latest breakthroughs in changing the paradigm with various efforts (Dwiyanto, 2015).

Bureaucratic reform must prioritize the implementation of every rule that applies to every institution. because the occurrence of bureaucratic reform focuses on what is the root of the problem in the governance that is being faced. In line with this, the government is building pilot units for other units. The concept used is the integrity zone in government, and NGOs (Non Government Organizations) in the context of preventing and eradicating corruption which is regulated in Presidential Regulation Number 81 of 2010. The commitment of government agencies to realize Corruption-Free Areas through Bureaucratic Reform, especially in terms of preventing corruption and improving the quality of public services, is explained in the Regulation of the Minister of State Apparatus Empowerment and Bureaucratic Reform Number 10 of 2019 concerning Guidelines for the Development of Integrity Zones Towards Corruption-Free Areas and Clean and Serving Bureaucratic Areas.

The implementation of the Integrity Zone Development at the Bekasi Regency Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service Office is guided by the Circular Letter of the Minister of State Apparatus Empowerment and Bureaucratic Reform Number 4 of 2025 concerning the Technical Proposal and Evaluation of the

Integrity Zone in 2025. Where the regional apparatus unit that carries out the development of the Integrity Zone to conduct an independent survey. This survey was conducted in order to understand and analyze public perceptions regarding anti-corruption issues and the quality of public services. So that data and information will be obtained regarding public views on efforts to eradicate corruption and evaluation of the quality of existing services.

In order to implement the assessment of the Development of the Integrity Zone towards a Corruption-Free Area and a Clean and Serving Bureaucratic Area in accordance with the Circular of the Minister of State Apparatus Empowerment and Bureaucratic Reform Number 4 of 2025 concerning the Technical Proposal and Evaluation of the Integrity Zone in 2025, the Bekasi Regency Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service Office conducts a Service Quality Perception Survey and an Anti-Corruption Perception Survey every month on all respondents who have received good services at the regional apparatus service counters.

METHODS

The type of research used by the author is descriptive qualitative which can explain and describe independently by analyzing qualitative data. The researcher explains the meaning and purpose of this research. Descriptive research is used based on the purpose of the research, namely analyzing and describing through the facts obtained, data obtained through researcher observations, interviews and documents or archives. The primary data source uses a purposive sampling technique which determines the key informant is the Head of the Service and the Secretary of the Service, in addition there are informants, namely the Head of Complaints. Head of Investment, functional officials Regency. The secondary data obtained from the literature, as well as official documents. Data analysis in the study uses the interactive model of Miles, Huberman, and Saldana (Sugiyono, 2017), namely data collection, data condensation, data presentation, drawing conclusions.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Implementation of Integrity Zone Development

Based on the results of a survey conducted in the development of the integrity zone, the anti-corruption perception value and the perception value of service quality at the Bekasi Regency Investment and Integrated One-Stop Service Office are perceived as Free from Corruption by the community using it. This can be seen from the Anti- Corruption Perception Index value obtained of 3.82 and the

Service Quality Perception Index value obtained of 3.80.

Change Management

Change management functions to systematically change the work mechanism and work culture of the organization. Especially in Regional Apparatus to be better, in accordance with the objectives of the integrity zone. In building a Work Unit to be better in accordance with the objectives and targets of the development of the Integrity Zone, the work unit must be able to systematically and consistently change the work mechanism, mindset, and work culture of individuals in the work unit that is built. The Bekasi Regency Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service Office has formed a Work Team with the commitment of the apparatus to the integrity zone development program by forming an integrity zone team consisting of 6 working groups (Work Groups) based on 6 areas of change in the development of the Integrity Zone. Furthermore, preparing an integrity zone development plan with priority targets that are relevant to the objectives of the integrity zone development. Monitoring and evaluation are carried out by paying attention to the implementation of the Integrity Zone development work plan and follow-up on the implementation of the Integrity Zone involving all work teams. However, during the implementation of monitoring and evaluation, it did not run periodically and was not followed up by the Work Team as explained by the Informant. In changing the mindset by making leaders as role models in the development of the Integrity Zone, then there is the determination of agents of change, building a work culture and mindset in the environment of the Bekasi Regency Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service Office and involving employees in the Integrity Zone development program.

Governance

The purpose of the Governance Arrangement is to increase efficiency and effectiveness as well as clear work procedures in the implementation of the Integrity Zone. In the implementation of the development of this Integrity Zone, there are targets to be achieved such as the use of information technology in the process of organizing government management, increasing the efficiency and effectiveness of the government management process and increasing performance in the Integrity Zone. The implementation of standard operating procedures refers to the business map, is evaluated and published. The Bekasi Regency Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service Office innovates the use of technology and information as an effort to support the implementation of the Electronic-Based Government System. This innovation shortens the procedural path so as to increase

the efficiency of service time. As a regional apparatus that supports the openness of public information, the Bekasi Regency Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service Office has a Public Information Management Officer Team that publishes on the website, Facebook, Instagram, but it is still not applied to banners or brochures.

Human Resource Management System Arrangement

Increasing the professionalism of human resources of the apparatus in each section is the goal of the arrangement of the human resources management system. This is supported for transparency and obtaining salaries and also guarantees of employee welfare. The competency-based recruitment and promotion system is also regulated in the arrangement of the implementation. Employee needs planning refers to the job map and the results of the workload analysis. Implementing monitoring and evaluation of employee needs plans. Internal mutation patterns with 3 indicators, namely policy formulation, implementation, and monitoring and evaluation. However, the Bekasi Regency Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service Office has not implemented an internal policy related to mutation patterns, but this has been done by evaluating employee recruitment placement.

The Bekasi Regency Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service Office has conducted a Training Need Analysis by compiling a list of employee training needs. In compiling employee competency development, it is compiled based on employee performance. Based on the Performance Agreement that has been compiled, individual performance indicators for each employee are based on work papers and in line with Employee Performance Targets. We measure individual performance monthly and annually. Then the results of individual performance assessments are used as the basis for providing allowances and determining exemplary employees. The purpose of the code of ethics is to encourage the implementation of main tasks and functions, improve employee discipline, ensure smooth implementation of tasks, improve work ethic, work quality and professional employee behavior. Measurement of this indicator is carried out by implementing disciplinary rules/code of ethics/code of employee behavior.

Strengthening Performance Accountability

Performance accountability is the manifestation of a government agency's obligation to be responsible for the success or failure of program and activity implementers in achieving the organization's mission and goals. The consequences of accountability can be in the form of awards or sanctions so that they can improve performance in providing services to the community. The involvement of the

leadership in this case the Head of the Bekasi Regency Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service Office and the staff involved in the preparation of planning documents includes work plan preparation meetings, evaluation meetings and budget preparation. The target in this indicator is to improve the performance of the Bekasi Regency Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service Office by preparing better Performance accountability reports and improving government integrity accountability.

Strengthening Supervision

Strengthening supervision aims to improve the implementation of clean and corruption-free governance. The targets to be achieved in strengthening supervision are compliance with financial management, increasing the effectiveness of financial management, increasing the status of the opinion of the Audit Board of Indonesia on financial management and decreasing the level of abuse of authority. The Bekasi Regency Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service Office has conducted a public campaign in several media about controlling gratification and conducting socialization. In addition, there is also the appointment of a coordinator for reporting gratification in its environment. Then, the existence of CCTV as supervision in the service area, then the implementation of the Government Internal Supervision System and providing space for resolving public complaints that can be quickly followed up by the Bekasi Regency Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service Office.

Improving the quality of Public Services

Service improvement is an effort to improve the quality and innovation of public services in agencies periodically according to the needs and expectations of the community. Improving the quality of public services is carried out to build public trust in the implementation of public services in order to improve facilities to improve public services.

The service standards for organizing licensing and non-licensing at the Bekasi Regency Investment and Integrated One-Stop Service Office stipulate the granting of access rights to integrated business service applications with Online Single Submission (OSS). In addition, there is also an announcement and determination of service standards. This announcement is published through the regional apparatus website. In addition, it provides training on services, provides rewards for the best employees, and provides information to several media and makes 3 innovations. However, these 3 innovations have not run optimally due to

the lack of socialization to the community or applicants.

The Bekasi Regency Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service Office conducts an independent assessment by conducting a public satisfaction survey which is conducted twice a year. The public satisfaction survey has 9 indicators, namely System Requirements, Mechanisms and Procedures, Costs/Tariffs, Product Specifications, Types of Services. Implementer Competence, Implementer Behavior, Handling complaints, suggestions and input facilities. The results of this public satisfaction survey are published through the Bekasi Regency Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service Office Public Satisfaction Index report.

The Role of Actors in Building Integrity Zones

Implementation of the Development of the Integrity Zone, the Head of the Bekasi Regency Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service Office decided on a work team with 6 areas of integrity zone change. These 6 areas are represented by all fields in the Bekasi Regency Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service Office. The team consists of the Person in Charge, chairman and coordinator and members. However, in determining the work team, there was a lack of clear tasks and functions for each area so that the performance was less focused by each coordinator and member. There are 5 roles of this work team's duties, namely catalyst. Catalyst means convincing employees in the work environment about the importance of conditions that are heading towards being better. Second, a solution provider who acts as a provider of alternative solutions to employees in the work environment. Third, a change driver who encourages and moves employees to participate. Fourth, a mediator to help smooth the process of changing the Integrity Zone, especially in terms of problems that arise. And finally, a liaison who is tasked with connecting between employees in the work environment. The roles of each field have been regulated in the Bekasi Regent Regulation on the Authority, position, organizational structure, duties and functions, and work procedures of the Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service Office. Structural position is a position that indicates the duties, responsibilities, authority, and rights of a Civil Servant in carrying out public service activities as well as government and development administration.

CONCLUSION

The conclusion from the research results and discussion outlined above can be drawn as follows:

1. The anti-corruption perception value and the service quality perception value at

the Bekasi Regency Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service Office are perceived as Free from Corruption by the community using it. This can be seen from the Anti- Corruption Perception Index Value obtained of 3.82 and the Service Quality Perception Index Value obtained of 3.80.

2. Implementation in the development of the Integrity Zone has been understood as a commitment that must be possessed by the Bekasi Regency Investment and One- Stop Integrated Service Office along with human resources to provide honest, accountable services that encourage increased performance of each individual who is part of the regulation. The behavior and attitude of the implementer also fully support the implementation of this regulation. The steps for change management, Arrangement of Governance, Arrangement of Human Resource Management System, Strengthening accountability, Strengthening supervision and Improving the Quality of Public Services.
3. Implementation of the Development of the Integrity Zone, all roles are classified as good, the form of the role of all actors involved in this regulation is to remind each other regarding this regulation, carry out excellent service that is clean, timely, fast, disciplined and in accordance with the Integrity Zone, all roles are classified as good, the form of the role of all actors involved in this regulation is to remind each other regarding this regulation, carry out excellent service that is clean, timely, fast, disciplined and in accordance with existing standard procedures and all employees are committed to avoiding illegal levies.

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